

CHANGES IN STOMACH MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS IN BRAIN INJURY

Salomov V.B.
Ochilov K.R.

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Bukhara State Medical Institute
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Cost:As a result of a traumatic injury of the central nervous system, complex pathophysiological mechanisms appear that disrupt the balance of the main nervous processes. Disorders of blood circulation in the brain, disruption of the circulation of the cerebrospinal fluid, brain tumors, etc. cause the appearance of these mechanisms. After the acute period of the disease, the recovery period begins, characterized by the restoration of impaired functions. Pathological symptoms observed during several years after the injury are recorded. Recurrent headaches, dizziness, autonomic-vascular symptoms, rapid fatigue, personality changes, memory impairment, and sometimes intellectual decline are among the most common symptoms. Depending on the location of the injury, the symptoms appear in paresis, paralysis, aphasia, deafness.

The purpose of the study:comparative study of morphometric parameters of stomach sections in normal and different periods of mild brain injury, development of correction methods.

Research methods and methods:An experimental scientific study was conducted on 200 adult white rats of both sexes weighing between 135 and 150 g. All white outbred rats were kept under normal vivarium conditions. Laboratory animals were kept in the vivarium of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. Rats were kept in special rooms (room temperature 20-24°C, humidity 60%, light 12 hours) according to the requirements for experimental animals.

Conclusions:

1. Peculiarities of the stomach of sexually mature and healthy white rats during late postnatal ontogenesis: see the ratio of the width of the stomach parts to the greater curvature efficient h/l was determined. This ratio was found to be 0.5 at the level of the gastric fundus, 0.35 at the body level, and 0.25 at the pyloric level. Important microscopic parameters of the stomach: the thickness of the mucous membrane in the body 325.44 ± 15.1 in the pyloric part of ± 11.1 μm It was equal to 5.9 μm . When studying TsYaNi, the number of nuclei at the intersection points of the ocular retina is on average 3.9 ± 0.18 , and the average

number of cytoplasms was 13.3 ± 1.01 . In this case, the cytoplasm-nuclear ratio was equal to 3.4 ± 0.23 on average.

2.A patent was obtained for a road traffic simulation device (Patent No. FAP 02271) to induce experimental BMEJ in non-white rats, and using a mild brain injury was called.

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